

Potentiometric Investigation on the Complexation Behaviour of Biologically Active *o*-Vanillinthiosemicarbazone towards Bivalent Metal Ions

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Thiosemicarbazones are well known for their biological and analytical properties¹. Lambrou² reported the thio and semicarbazone derivatives of *o*-vanillin as potential fungistatic and tuberculostatic agents. In view of the widespread applications of thiosemicarbazones and considering the biological potentialities of *o*-vanillinthiosemicarbazone (OVTSC) the present study was undertaken to determine the stability constants of bivalent metal ions with OVTSC at various ionic strength in 50% (v/v) dioxan medium.

Results and Discussion

The pK_a values of the ligand were obtained at $\mu=0.02, 0.05, 0.1$ and $0.2 M$ ($NaClO_4$) at $35 \pm 0.5^\circ$. In these studies the values of ligand dissociation constants and stability constants of the complexes (Table I) were found to decrease with increasing

ionic strength of the medium, in agreement with Debye-Hückel equation³,

$$pK_a [-A \sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \alpha \sqrt{\mu})] + C = pK_a$$

Thermodynamic stability constants obtained by extrapolation of a straight line plot of $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ to zero ionic strength are also given in Table I.

The stability constants of the metal complexes of OVTSC was found to follow the order: $Mn^{II} < Pb^{II} < Cd^{II} < Zn^{II} < Fe^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}$. The order is in good agreement with that found by Mellor and Maley⁴, and Irving and Williams⁵. In all the cases, except Mn and Cd, 1 : 2 complex is formed and $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are reported. In case of Mn and Cd, 1 : 1 complex is formed after that hydrolysis starts. In all cases it has been observed that $\log K_1 > \log K_2$. The complexes of OVTSC are of moderate stability.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH OVTSC AT $35 \pm 0.5^\circ$ AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTH

System	Stability constant	Ionic strength ($M NaClO_4$)				
		0.00*	0.02	0.05	0.1	0.2
OVTSC	$\log K_H$	10.50	10.21	10.02	9.89	9.75
Mn-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	5.52	5.33	5.33	5.06	4.05
	$\log K_2$	—	—	—	—	—
	S_{min}	—	0.002 41	0.008 72	0.001 46	0.004 16
Pb-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	7.10	6.92	6.87	6.72	6.47
	$\log K_2$	—	—	—	—	—
	S_{min}	—	0.002 61	0.012 10	0.001 80	0.006 36
Cd-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	7.47	7.24	7.07	6.99	6.77
	$\log K_2$	—	—	—	—	—
	S_{min}	—	0.003 72	0.019 76	0.025 58	0.002 74
Zn-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	7.78	7.54	7.41	7.28	7.03
	$\log K_2$	—	6.65	6.48	6.28	6.11
	S_{min}	—	0.003 43	0.001 05	0.004 62	0.008 95
Fe-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	8.47	8.19	8.00	7.84	7.74
	$\log K_2$	—	5.32	6.03	6.37	5.94
	S_{min}	—	0.017 91	0.007 75	0.004 23	0.012 41
Co-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	8.73	8.46	8.26	7.94	7.84
	$\log K_2$	—	6.59	7.23	6.28	6.53
	S_{min}	—	0.002 72	0.002 86	0.010 70	0.002 32
Ni-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	9.05	8.75	8.63	8.37	8.07
	$\log K_2$	—	8.15	8.02	7.59	7.34
	S_{min}	—	0.004 71	0.004 33	0.004 55	0.002 70
Cu-OVTSC	$\log K_1$	10.02	9.67	9.47	9.36	8.71
	$\log K_2$	—	8.38	8.23	8.01	7.88
	S_{min}	—	0.166 96	0.001 32	0.011 29	0.001 941

*Thermodynamic stability constant obtained by extrapolation of $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ to zero ionic strength.

Experimental

A Radiometer PHM83 pH meter with a single glass-calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements.

Preparation of ligand: *o*-Vanillinthiosemicarbazone (OVTSC) was prepared by the reported methods⁶. Its purity was checked by ir and ¹H nmr spectroscopy, elemental analysis and tlc, m.p. 207–09°.

The solution of OVTSC was prepared in 100% dioxan which was purified according to the known procedure⁷. All the metal ions solutions were prepared in double-distilled water from the corresponding sulphates or nitrates (AnalaR) and were standardised by conventional methods. Sodium perchlorate (Fluka) was used to keep the ionic strength constant for different sets. A solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH; Merck) in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan was used as titrant. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen (purity ~ 99.9%) atmosphere which was presaturated with 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan. All the measurements were made at 35 ± 0.5°. The following solutions (total volume = 19.60 ml) instead of 20 ml due to contraction in volume⁸ on mixing dioxan and water, were titrated potentiometrically against standard 0.04 M TMAH in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan to determine \bar{n} and pL values of the complexes: (i) 1 ml 0.04 M HClO₄ + 1 ml 2 M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.005 M K₂SO₄/KNO₃ + 7 ml H₂O + 10 ml dioxan, (ii) 1 ml 0.04 M HClO₄ + 1 ml 2 M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.005 M K₂SO₄/KNO₃ + 7 ml H₂O + 10 ml 0.01 M ligand, and (iii) 1 ml 0.04 M HClO₄ + 1 ml 2 M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.005 M M(II) + 7 ml H₂O + 10 ml 0.01 M ligand.

In other sets, requisite amount of NaClO₄ was added to maintain the ionic strength of 0.02, 0.05 and 0.2 M. From the titration curves of solution (i), (ii) and (iii) the values of \bar{n} and pL were calculated according to the method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁹ using a HP 9060 Fortran 77 computer. The corresponding values of stability constants were calculated using the weighted least-squares programme¹⁰. The weighted least-squares treatment determines that

set of β_n values which make the function,

$$U \left\{ U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y-x-nz) \beta_n x^n \right\} \quad (1)$$

nearest to zero by minimising

$$S \left\{ S = \sum_{i=1}^I U^2 (x_i y_i z_i) \right\} \quad (2)$$

with respect to variation in β_n . The function in equation (2) minimised (S_{\min}) has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with K degrees of freedom and with weights defined in accordance with Rydberg and Sullivan¹¹. It can be equated to χ^2 . The S_{\min} values for the different metal complexes are reported. The pK_a values and metal-ligand formation constants thus calculated are given in Table 1.

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